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**To,
Dear Pragathi Jogi**

This certificate confirms that **Pragathi Jogi** is the author of book chapter titled "**Review-Biological and Catalytic Activity of Metal Schiff Base Complexes**" of published book entitled "**Research Trends in Multidisciplinary Research (Volume - 31)**" having ISBN **978-93-5570-025-4**.

Yours Sincerely,

Akhil Gupta
Manager
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